

EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR TEACHING VOCABULARY TO PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Tojiboyev Isaqjon Madolimovich

Teacher at Fergana State University

Email: tojiboyev62@gmail.com

Abstract

In this article some strategies and techniques which can be used to teach vocabulary to primary school students are being described and researched on. In order to get the validity and actuality of the concepts which are being mentioned here, some literature are reviewed and given constructive conclusion. According to the results of the literature review, using some pictures, music, songs, realia and some interactive games are some of the best methods to achieve better results. Additionally, those techniques are beneficial to make the young language learners to get motivated and integrated to the language learning process. Afterwards, some recommendations and further information are provided in the discussion part of the article.

Key words: primary schools students, vocabulary teaching, interactive games.

Introduction

It is a fact that, main success in leaning a language can be seen in the level of speaking or listening skill acquisition. At the same time, the writing skills are also main skills which helps the language learner to use the language successfully [1]. However, according to the recent statistics one of the Asian country – Indonesia, where the English language is taught in mainly by reading and writing skills, is counted as a medium level country according to the quantity of the people who knows the language at a good level [2]. The leading places are taken by Malasia and Phillipin countries. This means that there is a strong needs and proof that teaching only most communicative skills is not enough to teach the language successfully, but there is also need for learning the grammar and vocabulary skills as well. In this article, some of the strategies are going to be explained and proposed to use in language teaching classes. In the same filed, many scientists gave their opinions, such as G.Kasimova said that learning and teaching vocabulary is as importan as teaching communicative and grammar skills in the acqusition of target language [3]. Another, linguist G.Kasimova, proposed that without learning vocabulary of the target language it is impossible to transfer the correct meaning even the big picture of the intended speech [4]. Another recommendation which is given by I.Tojiboyev is that teching vocabulary should be thought from the early ages of the language learners according to the concept of critical age hyposesis [5].

Teaching vocabulary to the students of primary shoools

Teaching vocabulary for primary school learners is different from teaching vocabulary to elementary or higher schools students according to different aspects [6]. Some of the reasons for that are young language learners want to learn the language by using some visual aids, playing some physical activities, playing some videos and singing some songs etc [7]. However, there are still many cases in primary learner classes about using grammar translation method, using only drilling activities. If the experience and skills of the language teacher are limited only with doing drilling and repetition activities for memorizing vocabulary, it will be reasonable barrier for learners to learn the language successfully [8]. As such, in the upcoming paragraphs some of the methods and strategies are recommended for language teachers to enhance their teaching skills and let their students to learn the language more at ease.

Research and method

In order to get a reliable results, the literature which are written in the last 5-7 years are taken to review and some results are recommended here for improving young language learners vocabulary skills [9]. One of them is using inductive method of using pictures and images to teach vocabulary [10]. According to the researchers, when using pictures to teach some vocabulary, the results of the teaching process is more successful than other types of teaching vocabulary. The picture 1 below can be considered one example for inductive way of teaching vocabulary using images of the objects.

Picture 1

Another scientists Mirzaaliyev I. also suggested that using digital or online games can also be a good way of teaching vocabulary to primary school students [11]. The results of the research showed that online gamified environment can enhance learners internal and external motivation according to some reasons. For example, firstly there will be competition environment which can create the feeling of competitiveness for children and they all may want to show their best and be winner in the online or digital activity [12]. Another fact is that it can give a way for metacognition in which learners can have quick feedback and information about their faults. This is also a good

way for language learners to gain a guidance for their further development in their language learning process [13].

Conclusion

The results of the contemporary researches have shown that vocabulary skills are important in the acquisition of a new language, especially in teaching second or foreign languages. In order to teach and guide young learners vocabulary skills needs special training, experience and special strategies from the language teachers. The strategies which are used by language learners should be attractive, effective, engaging and motivational. It is researched that using pictures and songs in teaching vocabulary skills is a good way in teaching primary school students.

References

1. Xoshimova, N. (2019). External factors of associations' individuality. *Scientific journal of the Fergana State University*, 2(2), 134-136.
2. Jalolov, J. (2012). Methods of teaching foreign languages. *T.,: Teacher*.
3. Makhmudovna, K. G. (2022). Creative Strategies to Improve Vocabulary Teaching. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(10), 259-261.
4. Kasimova, G. (2022). IMPORTANCE OF ICE BREAKING ACTIVITIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH. *Science and innovation*, 1(B7), 117-120.
5. Isaqjon, T. (2022). Strategies and techniques for improving EFL learners' reading skills. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(11), 94-99
6. Ahundjanova, M. (2022). THE NEEDS FOR IMPROVING LEARNERS' AUTONOMY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES—AS A KEY FACTOR TO BOOST LANGUAGE LEARNERS. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 390-392.
7. Mirzaev, A. B. U. (2022). IMPROVING EFL/ESL CLASSROOMS THROUGH USING ONLINE PLATFORMS: NEARPOD—AS AN EXAMPLE OF TOP-RATED ONLINE EDUCATIONAL PLATFORMS. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(4), 264-270.
8. Mirzayev, A., & Oripova, S. (2022). COMMUNICATIVE METHOD—A NEW APPROACH IN THE PRACTICE OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 778-783.
9. Qizi, I. G. X. (2022). Using phraseological units in theolinguistics.
10. Abdumutaljonovna, Pakirdinova Sharofat. "The function and peculiarities of advertising text in linguistics." *Confrencea 1.1* (2022).
11. Mirzaaliyev, I., & Oxunov, A. (2021). EKVIVALENTSIZ LEKSIKANING O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA IFODALANISHI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(6), 209-212.
12. Gafurova, N. (2020). Ҳозирги замон тилшунослигида “Термин” ва унга турлича ёндашувлар. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 1(1), 58-62.
13. Ahundjanova, M. A. (2020). METHODS AND METHODS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE. *Экономика и социум*, (11), 46-49.